

2D/2D Heterojunction Interfaces of 1T-MoS₂ and Ti₃C₂ MXene: Designing High-Performance Catalyst for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction

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Figure S1. (a) XRD of Ti₃C₂ and Ti₃AlC₂, (b) zoomed-in XRD of composites from 5 to 30°, (c) TGA curves of 2H-MoS₂ and 1T-MoS₂, (d) XRD of Ti₃C₂ and Ti₃AlC₂, and (e) SEM of delaminated Ti₃C₂ MXene.

Figure S2. (a) TEM of Ti₃C₂, (b) HRTEM of Ti₃C₂ (Inset: SAED of Ti₃C₂), (c, d) TEM and HRTEM of 2H-MoS₂, (e, f) TEM and HRTEM of 1T-MoS₂, (g) EDS spectra of Ti₃C₂ and TM-1 and their corresponding O/Ti atomic % ratio

Figure S3. (a) XPS survey spectra of Ti₃C₂ and composites, high-resolution XPS spectra of Ti₃C₂: (b) Ti 2p, (c) C 1s, and (d) O 1s, High-resolution XPS spectra of Mo 3d in: (e) 2H-MoS₂, and (f) 1T-MoS₂, High-resolution XPS spectra of S 2p in: (g) 2H-MoS₂, and (h) 1T-MoS₂

Table S1a. Report the full-width-half-maximum (FWHM) values for the XPS deconvoluted peaks of Mo 3d

Sample	1T 3d _{5/2}	1T 3d _{3/2}	2H 3d _{5/2}	2H 3d _{3/2}	Mo (VI) 3d _{5/2}	Mo (VI) 3d _{3/2}	S 2s
TM-1	1.28	1.28	1.83	1.83	5.35	5.35	2.68
TM-2	1.24	1.24	2.00	2.00	3.60	3.60	2.52
TM-5	1.24	1.24	1.91	1.91	4.42	4.42	2.50
TM-10	1.22	1.22	2.18	2.18	3.80	3.80	2.51

The 5/2 and 3/2 components of the same type of electrons are constrained, meaning their FWHMs are forced to be equal. The lower FWHMs of the 1T phase correspond to its conducting, metallic behavior, confirming the assignment of the 1T/2H phase.

These values fall within expected ranges for chemically distinct Mo species in MoS₂-based materials. The narrower FWHMs of the 1T-MoS₂ components (~1.22-1.28 eV) relative to those of the 2H-MoS₂ peaks (~1.83-2.18 eV) are consistent with the more delocalized electronic structure of the 1T phase, which arises from its metallic, octahedrally coordinated Mo environment. In contrast, the broader 2H peaks reflect its semiconducting character and the increased chemical disorder associated with 2H domains in the mixed-phase composite. Furthermore, the significantly broader FWHMs for the Mo (VI) peaks (3.6-5.35 eV) likely reflect the contribution from multiple surface oxidation species.

Table S1b. Deconvoluted peak areas of the S 2p region from XPS analysis and calculated 1T phase content of MoS₂.

Sample	1T S2p_{3/2}	1T S2p_{1/2}	2H S2p_{3/2}	2H S2p_{1/2}	% 1T-MoS₂
TM-1	31495.5	16094.2	4132.1	2111.5	89
TM-2	25484.5	13022.6	3701.8	1891.6	87
TM-5	16942.8	8657.8	3191.0	1630.6	84
TM-10	26902.2	13747.0	5163.4	2638.5	83

The percentage of 1T-MoS₂ was determined by integrating the areas of the deconvoluted S 2p_{3/2} and S 2p_{1/2} peaks corresponding to both the 1T and 2H phases of MoS₂. The 1T phase content was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{1T-MoS}_2 (\%) = (A_{1T} / (A_{2H} + A_{1T})) \times 100$$

where A_{1T} and A_{2H} represent the total integrated areas of the S 2p peaks attributed to the 1T and 2H phases, respectively.

Figure S4. Cyclic voltammograms obtained from the non-faradic region of: (a) Ti_3C_2 , (b) 2H-MoS_2 , (c) 1T-MoS_2 , (d) TM-1, (e) TM-2, (f) TM-5, (g) TM-10 at different scan rates in $0.5\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$, and (h) ECSA normalized LSV of all catalysts

Figure S5. Equivalent circuit used to simulate the Nyquist plot where: R_s : solution resistance, R_f and CPE_1 are related to the porosity of the electrode; R_{ct} : charge transfer resistance, CPE_2 is

related to the interface between catalyst and electrolyte; CPE represents constant phase element.

(EIS data fitted by ZView software)

Figure S6. (a) Stability test of TM-1 under constant current density of 10 mA cm⁻² for 50 h, (b) Stability test of TM-1 under constant current density of 200 mA cm⁻² for 24 h (inset: SEM of TM-1 after stability test), (c) LSV, and (d) EIS of TM-1 before and after stability test under J= 200 mA cm⁻²

Table S2. Comparison of the electrocatalytic performance of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2/1\text{T-MoS}_2$ with (1T, 2H) MoS_2 and other MoS_2 -MXene-based materials for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER).

Catalysts	Overpotential η_{10} [mV]	Tafel Slope [mV·dec ⁻¹]	Mass loading	Synthesis method	Electrolyte	References
$\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2/1\text{T-MoS}_2$	248	55	0.32 mg cm ⁻²	Hydrothermal	0.5 M H_2SO_4	This work
$\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2/\text{MoS}_2$ (1T-2H)	280	83.8	0.44 mg cm ⁻²	Hydrothermal+ Interfacial Assembly	0.5 M H_2SO_4	¹
$\text{MoS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$	400	68	0.35	hydrothermal method	0.5 M H_2SO_4	²
TCO/ MoS_2	269	82	3.8	One-pot solvothermal synthesis	0.5 M H_2SO_4	³
MoS_2 QDs/ $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$	220	72	0.354	Electrostatic self-assembly	0.5 M H_2SO_4	⁴
MoS_2 -MXene	307	68.5	-	hydrothermal method	0.5 M H_2SO_4	⁵
$\text{Ti}_3\text{CN}(\text{OH})_x@\text{MoS}_2$	120	64	0.408	Hydrothermal method	0.5 M H_2SO_4	⁶
$\text{Mo}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{C}_3\text{T}_x/\text{MoS}_2$	298	112	0.2	microwave-assisted hydrothermal method	1 M KOH	⁷
$\text{MoS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ MXene	421	217	-	Hydrothermal method	1 M NaOH	⁸
$\text{MoS}_2/\text{Nb}_2\text{CT}_x$	127	56.3	-	hydrothermal method	0.5 M H_2SO_4	⁹
MoS_2 - $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$	152	70	0.28	combining liquid nitrogen-freezing and subsequent annealing.	0.5 M H_2SO_4	¹⁰
MoS_2 - Nb_2CT_x	141	93.4	-	hydrothermal method	1 M KOH	⁹
$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MoS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene	123	71	-	hydrothermal synthesis	0.5 M H_2SO_4	¹¹

2H-MoS ₂	369	137	0.26 ug.cm ⁻²	solid-state reaction and annealing	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	12
2H-MoS ₂ 1T-2H MoS ₂	342 212	78 131	-	CVD	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	13
1T-MoS ₂	230	58.47	0.46 mg cm ⁻²	Solvothermal	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	14
1T-MoS ₂	235	106	1 mg cm ⁻²	Hydrothermal	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	15
1T/2H MoS ₂	255	44	0.285 mg cm ⁻²	Hydrothermal	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	16
p-MoS ₂	260	53.6	0.285 mg cm ⁻²	micro-reaction	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	17
1T-MoS ₂	292	55.7	0.28 mg cm ⁻²	Hydrothermal	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	18

Figure S7. Bar chart comparing the Tafel slopes of MoS₂-MXene-based HER catalysts. The Ti₃C₂/1T-MoS₂ catalyst from this work is highlighted in red. Reference numbers correspond to those listed in Table S2.

Table S3 EIS fitting parameters from the equivalent circuit for different samples

Samples	R_s (Ω)	R_f (Ω)	CPE₁ (S s⁻ⁿ)	R_{ct} (Ω)	CPE₂ (S s⁻ⁿ)
1T-MoS₂	1.3	15.9	9.18E-7	133	3.69E-3
TM-1	1	9.3	9.360E-7	91	9.070E-3
TM-2	1.1	20.1	5.71E-7	181	4.356E-4
TM-5	1.2	22.4	4.08E-7	238	6.009E-4
TM-10	1.4	28.6	1.831E-7	428	2.79E-4

Table S 4. The estimated C_{dl} , and the corresponding ECSA of different samples

Catalysts	C_{dl} (mF cm ⁻²)	ECSA (cm ²)
TM-1	14	350
TM-2	11.8	295
TM-5	5.45	136.25
TM-10	4.5	112.5
1T-MoS ₂	6.16	154
2H-MoS ₂	1.82	45.5
Ti ₃ C ₂	0.8	20

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